

The field and the "research subfield of Sociology Teaching" in Brazil

Abstract

This article presents an overview of recent advances in the field of Sociology Teaching in Brazil, with an emphasis on its research subfield. Based on the analysis of a set of investigations, the composition of these social spheres is outlined, highlighting their structures, the agents operating within them, and the symbolic capital that is valued. The study reveals the growth of academic production, the establishment of specialized journals, the organization of scientific events, and the formation of researcher networks. However, challenges persist, such as the concentration of production among a few authors, regional inequalities in the distribution of research groups, the low international visibility of the subfield, and the need for stronger connections between the academic and educational settings.

Keywords: Field. Subfield. Sociology Teaching. Brazil.

Cristiano das Neves Bodart

Federal University of

Alagoas (UFAL)

E-mail:

cristianobodart@gmail.com

Introduction

Over the past two decades, the Teaching of Sociology¹ in Brazil has undergone a process of consolidation and expansion, driven by curricular changes, advances in teacher training, and the growth of academic production focused on this area. The inclusion of Sociology as a mandatory subject in high school, instituted in 2008, marked a turning point in its institutionalization, increasing the demand for specialized teachers, teaching materials, and research on pedagogical practices. However, this

¹ It is important to note that we use the capitalized form "Teaching" to distinguish it from a meaning strictly tied to classroom practice. Although the term "Education" could be conceptually broader, the use of "Teaching" is well established in the literature of this field. Replacing it would require a more extensive discussion, which is beyond the scope of this work. Thus, we use "Teaching" to encompass not only classroom activity, but also aspects such as curriculum, teacher training, working conditions, scientific production, public programs and policies, and other structural elements of the field.

progress has not been without challenges, as the presence of Sociology in the curriculum has been the subject of political and academic disputes, as well as repeated attempts to reduce its class hours or remove it from the curriculum framework.

Given this context, a social sphere emerges that has been referred to by several researchers - such as Bodart and Cigales (2017), Pereira (2019), Mocelin (2020), and Oliveira (2023) - as the Field of Sociology Teaching. Here, we aim to show that this field is not limited to teaching practice, but encompasses broader issues such as curriculum design, educational policies, the production of teaching materials, and teacher training. Within this broader space, we observe the development of a research subfield of Sociology Teaching, characterized by theoretical and methodological systematization around the discipline, as well as academic disputes concerning the legitimization of this knowledge within the scientific field.

This article aims to present a set of constitutive elements of the Field of Sociology Teaching and its research subfield, highlighting its structures, the agents operating within it, and the symbolic capital that circulates in this space. Drawing on a Bourdieusian approach, the goal is to understand how this subfield has been institutionalizing in Brazil, what its main challenges are, and how researcher networks dedicated to this topic are structured. To this end, the transformations that have taken place in recent decades in relation to the Teaching of Sociology are examined.

In the first part of the article, we seek to highlight the constitutive elements of the Field of Sociology Teaching. In the second part, we focus the analysis on recent data drawn from a set of studies I have conducted in recent years, in addition to contributions from other researchers who have helped advance the field. The goal is to provide an overview of the research subfield of Sociology Teaching in Brazil, outlining its configuration and main dynamics.

By reflecting on the consolidation of this subfield, the article contributes to a fundamental debate about the direction of Sociology as a school subject and its place within the educational and academic fields. Understanding its dynamics and disputes is essential to strengthening its presence in high school education and

enhancing research in the area, ensuring greater institutional recognition and expanding its impact on the civic formation of students.

1 The Field of Sociology Teaching in Brazil

By "field of Sociology Teaching," we understand the social sphere composed of a set of structures, agents, and products that revolve around school-based Sociology. It is an abstraction, guided by a Bourdieusian perspective (Bourdieu, 2001).² This field is configured as a broad yet convergent community, composed of different social agents, including high school Sociology teachers, high school students, undergraduate students in Social Sciences/Sociology, researchers in Sociology Teaching, and producers of educational resources. In addition, it encompasses spaces and institutions dedicated to teacher training, curricular regulation, and the implementation of the discipline in schools.

The field of Sociology Teaching encompasses both the pedagogical practices developed in schools and the academic and political disputes surrounding its presence in the curriculum. From an analytical perspective, this conception reinforces the idea that Sociology Teaching is not limited to classroom practice, but constitutes a dynamic social space in which collaborations, struggles for recognition, processes of legitimizing the discipline, and influence on educational policies take place.

In the same vein, Oliveira (2023) broadly outlines the constitution of this field, its agents, and the disputes that traverse it. According to the author, this social sphere has played a significant role in producing specific forms of socialization, contributing to the internalization of certain social structures and the formation of lasting dispositions.

According to Mocelin (2020), this field acquires a certain degree of autonomy as a trajectory of occupying spaces and a structuring—though intermittent—

² By choice, we will not highlight the theoretical foundations that guide the reflections presented here. For that, see Bodart (2024a; 2024b; 2024c).

narrative takes shape, guiding and connecting the actions of different agents, and driving movements of expansion, organization, and accumulation of experience.

Based on this conceptualization, it can be stated that the Field of Sociology Teaching has significantly expanded in Brazil over the past two decades. Although the discipline was included in the official secondary school curriculum at the end of the 19th century, its presence remained intermittent and fragmented throughout the 20th century. Between 1925 and 1942, it was part of the junior high curriculum, gradually returning in the 1980s (Azevedo, 2014), and becoming mandatory across all Brazilian high schools only in 2008. During this period, its presence was diffuse—either with its content diluted into other Humanities subjects or as Sociology of Education within secondary-level teacher training programs.

In recent decades, even during its period of mandatory inclusion, the subject has faced—and continues to face - threats of removal from the mandatory curriculum or reductions in its class hours (Bodart; Feijó, 2020). Sociology taught in Brazilian high schools draws from three core disciplines: Sociology, Anthropology, and Political Science, as highlighted by Bispo (2012) in his analysis of curricula from 14 Brazilian states.

According to the 2022 School Census (INEP, 2023), Brazil had 46,856 Sociology teachers and a total of 7,877,394 students enrolled in high school, with 6.6 million (84.2%) in state schools, 232,000 (3%) in federal schools, and approximately 971,500 (12.3%) in private institutions. This group not only represents a key audience for the dissemination of Sociology but also forms the base of future entrants into undergraduate Social Sciences and Sociology teaching and academic programs.

The inclusion of Sociology as a mandatory high school subject starting in 2008 led to a growing demand for teachers in the field, which in turn spurred the creation and expansion of undergraduate programs in Social Sciences and Sociology. According to the Ministry of Education's system (e-MEC)³, there are currently 144 Social Sciences programs in operation, 107 of which are in-person and 37 offered via

³ Available at: <https://emec.mec.gov.br/emec/nova>

Distance Education (EaD). Additionally, there are 61 undergraduate programs specifically in Sociology teaching, with 29 offered in-person and 32 through EaD.

Another key factor in strengthening the field was the inclusion of Sociology in the National Textbook and Teaching Materials Program (Programa Nacional do Livro e do Material Didático -PNLD) in 2012. This initiative enabled the free distribution of textbooks to public school students. Although the program was aimed at students, it also contributed to enhancing teaching practices by providing materials that structured the content being taught and offered pedagogical guidelines through teacher manuals.

That same year, the Brazilian Associação Brasileira de Ensino de Ciências Sociais (Abecs) was founded. It brings together undergraduate Social Sciences teaching students, Sociology teachers from both basic and higher education, and researchers on the subject, promoting a range of activities, especially the biennial National Congress. This institution holds significant political and academic relevance in Brazil for both the professionalization of the field and resistance to attacks on Sociology teaching (Pereira, 2017), uniting social agents who continue to work in collaboration with the Brazilian Sociological Society (SBS), and even with other scientific associations such as the Associação Brasileira de Antropologia (ABA) and the Associação Brasileira de Ciência Política (ABCP) (Oliveira & Cigales, 2019). While we will not retrace its history here, it is important to note that this entity emerged within the academic field during a moment of greater receptiveness to both basic education teachers and the topic of Sociology teaching - albeit still insufficient.

The training of Sociology teachers has been bolstered by the Programa de Iniciação à Docência (PIBID), which supports student retention and brings Social Sciences teacher education closer to the school environment. The program provides financial aid, promoting stronger connections between theory and practice in Sociology teaching. These scholarships have helped spark greater interest among university professors in engaging more closely with schools.

Teacher training guidelines approved in recent decades have also encouraged stronger ties between teacher education programs and school realities, as well as educational themes. Conselho Nacional de Educação (CNE) n. 2/2015 CNE No. 2/2015, for instance, led many Social Sciences degree programs to integrate subject-specific training with pedagogical training. As a result, the traditional “3 + 1” model - in which students took three years of specialized coursework followed by an additional year of pedagogical training, typically disconnected from the original program - was progressively replaced by fully integrated licensure programs. This shift diminished the strictly academic nature of these programs and strengthened their identity as teacher training courses.

Despite these advances, Sociology Teaching remains vulnerable to attempts to remove it from the required curriculum, such as with Law No. 13,415/2017, known as the 2017 High School Reform, which amended the Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação Nacional (LDB). However, this reform was modified in 2024 by Law No. 14,945/2024 (Brazil, 2024), which, despite making only minor changes, reaffirmed the inclusion of Sociology as a mandatory subject in high school.

In 2019, the Base Nacional Comum para a Formação Inicial de Professores da Educação Básica (BNC-Formação) was approved (Brazil, 2019), introducing guidelines that contrast with those of Resolution CNE No. 2/2015. It emphasized a teacher education model based on the repetition of practices at the expense of integrating theory and practice (Bazzo; Scheibe, 2019).

Another setback occurred in 2022 when the PNLD stopped selecting subject-specific textbooks for students and instead began distributing materials organized by area of knowledge. This negatively affected Sociology teaching, whose teacher training is essentially disciplinary. Due to widespread criticism, the model was revised and returned to a disciplinary format. The textbooks - currently under review - will be distributed in 2026.

Furthermore, the termination of the Pedagogical Residency Program represented a significant loss for the quality of teacher training and the retention of

students in teaching programs. This initiative benefited Social Sciences licensure programs in public universities by providing scholarships to students, coordinators, and public school teachers who hosted them in schools.

This overview is essential for understanding the expansion of the social agents involved in Sociology Teaching and its consolidation as a research subject, making it possible to identify a specific subfield within this area, which will be addressed in the next section.

2 The Research Subfield of Sociology Teaching in Brazil

The "research subfield of Sociology Teaching," as we understand it - drawing on a Bourdieusian perspective (Bourdieu, 2001) - constitutes an analytical segment of the broader "Field of Sociology Teaching." It is only a fraction of the larger field, yet it operates with a distinct internal logic, though still related to and dependent on it. This research subfield is understood as a more narrowly defined sphere within the broader universe, composed specifically of agents and structures connected to the scientific community. Its main feature is the theoretical and methodological systematization of knowledge about the teaching of the discipline, addressing themes such as curriculum, teacher training, pedagogical practices, and educational policies.

The research subfield of Sociology Teaching does not exhibit full autonomy from the broader field, but it does have its own operational logic, with internal rules and disputes for academic recognition. Researchers operating within this space seek to accumulate scientific capital (though not exclusively), which is manifested in the publication of books, articles, and book chapters, the organization of thematic dossiers, participation in specialized academic events—especially as keynote speakers - coordination of working groups (GTs), the acquisition of research grants, affiliations with graduate programs, and other forms of scientific output.

Although the research subfield maintains a strong connection with the broader Field of Sociology Teaching, and remains interdependent with it, the academic subfield also influences debates and the formulation of policies on the teaching of

Sociology. Conversely, the broader field impacts the themes and problems that researchers in the subfield investigate. Many of the agents striving for distinction within the research subfield are also active in the broader field, with some serving as authors of textbooks or pedagogical works (Oliveira, 2023). The pursuit of distinction in both segments of this social sphere occurs due to the significant proximity between the academic and school-based fields related to Sociology teaching (Oliveira, 2023). This is clearly visible in specialized conferences where both higher education professionals and basic education teachers participate. Another point of convergence can be seen in the involvement of researchers in curricular policy debates and in their participation in the PNLD as evaluators of Sociology textbooks.

The research subfield of Sociology Teaching includes a set of structural elements that demonstrate its process of formation and consolidation. Currently, in Brazil, there are three specialized journals dedicated to the teaching of Sociology, in addition to other academic journals that regularly publish articles on the subject, such as *Revista Café com Sociologia*⁴. Interestingly, these three journals are linked to different types of institutions that make up the Field of Sociology Teaching: universities, schools, and scientific organizations.

The *Cadernos da Associação Brasileira do Ensino de Ciências Sociais*⁵, founded in 2017, is managed by the Abecs, reflecting the role of a scientific entity in consolidating this field. Meanwhile, *Perspectiva Sociológica*⁶ is affiliated with Colégio Pedro II, representing the engagement of educational institutions in the production and dissemination of knowledge. In turn, the journal *Ensino de Sociologia em Debate*⁷ is published by the Universidade Estadual de Londrina (UEL) and is linked to a specialization program in Sociology Teaching, demonstrating the role of universities in research and teacher education in this area.

⁴ Available at: <https://revistacafecomsociologia.com/revista/index.php/revista>

⁵ Available at: <http://cabecs.com.br/index.php/cabecs/index>

⁶ Available at: <https://www.cp2.g12.br/ojs/index.php/PS/index>

⁷ Available at: <http://www.uel.br/revistas/lenpes-pibid/>

These journals represent a significant advancement in the dissemination of research within the field of Sociology Teaching. In addition to academic journals, the Editora Café com Sociologia⁸, founded in 2019, has played a central role in the scientific dissemination of the area, currently concentrating the largest volume of published books on the subject. Among these, the Dicionário do Ensino de Sociologia (Brunetta; Bodart; Cigales, 2020) stands out. This work, which involved contributions from 84 researchers, “[...] offers us a picture of academic research on pedagogical [and research] work in the school subject of Sociology” (Schnekenberg, 2020, p. 154).

Other constituent elements of the research subfield of Sociology Teaching include two specialized national biennial events: the Encontro Nacional de Ensino de Sociologia na Educação Básica (Eneseb), organized by the Sociedade Brasileira de Sociologia, and the Congresso Nacional da Abecs, promoted by that organization. The Eneseb will hold its ninth edition in 2025, while the Congresso Nacional da Abecs held its sixth edition in 2024. These events play a fundamental role in scientific dissemination and in strengthening research networks, also serving as launching points for the publication of collections and thematic dossiers in academic journals. Moreover, as highlighted by Oliveira (2023), the Eneseb has become a space of symbolic consecration for agents operating within the field of Sociology Teaching.

The emergence of the Mestrado Profissional em Ciências Sociais para o Ensino Médio, affiliated with the Fundação Joaquim Nabuco (FUNDAJ), represents a significant step forward in teacher qualification and research on Sociology teaching. It paved the way for the creation of the Mestrado Profissional em Sociologia (ProfSocio), aimed at the continuing education of teachers (Oliveira & Cigales, 2019). In recent decades, several *stricto sensu* graduate programs have welcomed research on Sociology teaching. Various studies have been dedicated to analyzing the theses and dissertations produced within these programs, examining the volume of work, the topics addressed, the profiles of the authors, and the graduate programs to which

⁸ Available at: <https://www.editoracafecomsociologia.com/>

they are affiliated. Among these are notable studies by Handfas (2013), Bodart & Cigales (2017), and Antunes, Garcia & Alves (2018). These analyses highlight a crucial point: the significant growth of academic production, particularly since 2008, when Sociology became a mandatory subject in Brazilian high schools.

In 2020, at least 21 laboratórios de ensino de Sociologia were identified as being dedicated to research and teacher training (Pereira, 2020). Usually linked to outreach projects, these labs aim to bring future teachers closer to school environments and the specific issues surrounding the teaching of Sociology, while also serving as important spaces for empirical research. This dynamic illustrates the strong interconnection between the research subfield of Sociology Teaching and its broader social sphere - the field of Sociology Teaching.

In Brazil, much of the research in the area originates from grupos de pesquisa registered with the Diretório do Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq), as research funding is often contingent upon such registration. Undergraduate research scholarships distributed through the Programa Institucional de Bolsas de Iniciação Científica (PIBIC) are an example of this dependency. As such, the number of research groups working on a particular theme may indicate the expansion or contraction of a research subfield. Based on this assumption, Bodart, Santos, and Nascimento (2024) conducted an analysis of the research groups registered in the CNPq Directory in 2023, focusing on Sociology Teaching. The data revealed significant growth in the number of groups in recent years. A total of 28 groups were identified with research lines or keywords directly related to the teaching of Sociology. This number represents a notable increase compared to the previous survey conducted by Neuhold in 2014, which recorded only 13 groups (Bodart, Santos & Nascimento, 2024). This growth indicates a greater institutionalization of the subfield, reflecting both the increase in scientific production and growing academic interest in the area - especially following the 2008 mandate that made Sociology a required subject in high school.

The analysis of the territorial distribution of research groups revealed a significant concentration in the South and Southeast regions, while the Northeast, despite having a considerable number of undergraduate programs in Social Sciences, still shows a limited presence of formally registered groups. This data suggests that although academic production on Sociology Teaching has grown in the country, the consolidation of research groups occurs unevenly, reinforcing regional inequalities already observed in other studies on Brazilian academic output.

Another relevant aspect identified was the composition of researchers affiliated with these groups. The study revealed a predominance of PhD holders in Sociology or Social Sciences, indicating the subfield's alignment with the broader area of Social Sciences, although Education also appears as a relevant formative sphere. Additionally, a relative gender balance was observed among researchers, with a slight male predominance in group leadership. However, the analysis of scientific production showed that article publication on Sociology Teaching is concentrated among a few researchers, which may indicate challenges in diversifying authorship and expanding the network of active researchers in the field.

A key finding from the study (Bodart, Santos & Nascimento, 2024) was the absence of formal international collaborations within the analyzed groups. This suggests that Sociology Teaching still functions as a predominantly national subfield, lacking established participation in international research networks. This characteristic may hinder the strengthening of the subfield, considering the importance of knowledge exchange and academic collaboration for the consolidation of emerging areas.

The results, therefore, indicate that Sociology Teaching has been consolidating as a legitimate space for academic production, with a growing number of researchers and groups dedicated to the topic. However, challenges remain - particularly regarding the regional distribution of research groups, authorship diversification, the strengthening of collaborative networks, and the internationalization of the subfield. The continued growth of this subfield will depend on researchers' ability to expand

institutional spaces, increase the participation of new agents, and establish broader connections both nationally and internationally.

In another recent study I conducted (Bodart, 2024a), I sought to examine the scientific production within the research subfield of Sociology Teaching in Brazil. The findings revealed a recent growth in output, but with a strong concentration in terms of both authorship and publishing venues. As highlighted by Oliveira (2023), the production of articles, in addition to theses and dissertations on Sociology Teaching, has become a tool for social legitimation - making it a key element in understanding this subfield.

The bibliometric analysis I carried out (Bodart, 2024a) indicated that, despite an increase in the number of published articles, this expansion has not occurred evenly, revealing an unequal distribution of productivity among researchers and academic journals. The data show that most articles were produced by a small number of authors. Among the 1,102 researchers identified, 83.01% published only one article on the subject. On the other hand, just 7% of authors published three or more articles, indicating that sustained scientific production on Sociology Teaching is highly concentrated within a small group of researchers. This concentration of authorship can be explained, in part, by institutional research conditions, since the most prolific authors are mostly affiliated with graduate programs and universities, where there is greater incentive and demand for academic publication.

In the same study (Bodart, 2024a), it was also evident that the distribution of articles across journals reinforces this idea of concentration in the research subfield of Sociology Teaching. Although 205 journals published at least one paper on the topic, 96% of those journals published only a single article, and a very small number of journals were responsible for a large portion of the publications. Another aspect revealed was the importance of thematic dossiers as a relevant strategy for giving visibility to the topic of Sociology Teaching (Oliveira, 2023).

This high concentration of both authors and journals can be seen as a sign of fragility in the subfield, as its sustainability depends on a limited group of

researchers and a small number of dissemination platforms. This situation may create challenges for the consolidation of Sociology Teaching as an autonomous academic subfield, limiting its diversification and the entry of new researchers. The study's results showed that Sociology Teaching in Brazil has been asserting itself as a legitimate area of inquiry, but one still marked by inequalities in access to academic production and publishing opportunities. It seems that the future of this subfield will depend on its ability to expand institutional spaces, encourage the participation of new researchers, and ensure a more balanced distribution of academic output - preventing research on the topic from becoming restricted to a small group of specialists and a limited number of journals.

Still concerning the agents “playing the game” in the research subfield of Sociology Teaching, some interesting analyses emerge regarding the contribution of women to the scientific development of this sphere. In another study I recently conducted (Bodart, 2024b), I analyzed the participation of women in the research subfield of Sociology Teaching, using scientometric approaches and Pierre Bourdieu's Theory of Fields. The study showed that, although women are numerically predominant in academic production on Sociology Teaching, they still face structural challenges that limit their recognition and access to institutional resources.

The data from this study (Bodart, 2024b) revealed that women researchers make up the majority of authors in papers about the Teaching of Sociology, accounting for 56.63% of the total identified publications. This predominance remains consistent over time, both in the early period of the subfield's formation, up to 2012, and between 2013 and 2023. However, the analysis of individual productivity shows that male researchers still hold a significant share of the most cited articles and publish in higher volume, as evidenced in another previously mentioned study (Bodart, 2024a). Only two women appear among the ten most productive researchers in the subfield, revealing an inequality in the distribution of impactful authorship.

Despite this strong female presence in knowledge production, the research highlights that women face institutional barriers that limit their academic

recognition. An example of this is the lower presence of women researchers among the recipients of CNPq Research Productivity Grants. None of the main female authors identified in the study received this type of funding, reflecting the difficulties women face in accessing resources that bring greater prestige and continuity in research (Bodart, 2024a). This reflects a broader scenario in Brazilian science, where women represent a smaller proportion of high-level scholarship holders, even when their academic productivity is equivalent to that of men. We must not lose sight of the fact that “university power can only be accumulated and maintained at the cost of a constant and significant expenditure of time” (Bourdieu, 2017), and in this context, women end up facing greater difficulties compared to men—whether due to the social imposition of family and domestic tasks, maternity leaves, or especially the absence of academic policies that promote gender equity⁹.

Another relevant aspect of the research is the analysis of collaboration among women researchers. Most of the articles written by women are authored individually or in partnership with male researchers, with all-female co-authorship networks being rare. Overall, the structure of collaboration in the subfield does not reflect a strengthening of networks among women researchers, which hinders the consolidation of a space with greater female leadership and the strengthening of social capital among them.

The results indicate that, although women play a central role in the production of knowledge about the Teaching of Sociology, they still face symbolic and institutional barriers to achieving greater academic recognition. The study suggests that the persistence of these inequalities is related to the structure of the scientific field, which has historically favored male trajectories and imposes additional difficulties for women to access spaces of greater prestige and funding.

⁹ A widely publicized and emblematic case in Brazil in 2023 involved the rejection of a research productivity grant application submitted by a female researcher, in which the negative review questioned the interruption in her academic output due to maternity leave. After the case gained public attention, CNPq changed its policy, establishing that an additional two years would be added to the evaluation period for productivity for each childbirth or adoption.

In light of this scenario, the research (Bodart, 2024a) reinforces the need for gender equity policies in academia, including increased funding for women researchers, the promotion of collaborative networks among women, and the strengthening of institutional mechanisms that value their contributions. Only by overcoming these barriers will it be possible to ensure that the participation of women in the subfield of the Teaching of Sociology is reflected not only in their quantitative output but also in their recognition and value within the scientific field.

With regard to co-authorship networks, I conducted a study (Bodart, 2024c) in which I analyzed the networks of scholarly collaboration in the Teaching of Sociology, aiming to identify micro-networks of researchers and their main connecting agents. Also using an approach based on Pierre Bourdieu's concept of social capital and methods of co-authorship network analysis, I mapped the structure of academic interactions and highlighted the formation of connections among researchers working in the subfield of the Teaching of Sociology.

The results indicated that there is a set of interconnected micro-networks that form a larger network, in which a few researchers play a central role in articulating these connections (Bodart, 2024c). The formation of these micro-networks is associated with factors such as institutional proximity, participation in specialized academic events, and involvement in academic journals focused on the Teaching of Sociology. It was found that the most active researchers in co-authorships are also often involved in coordinating working groups at conferences and managing academic journals, which gives them a role as catalysts within the subfield. At the same time, they gain social prestige, leading them to become even more engaged in the subfield, as Bourdieu (2017; 2020) notes when discussing the forces that drive social agents in the academic field.

Another significant finding of the research (Bodart, 2024c) is that authorship collaboration occurs unevenly, being concentrated in certain hubs and reflecting the asymmetrical distribution of social capital within the field. Some researchers build broader and more diverse networks, while others maintain collaborations limited to a few colleagues. The research also shows that public universities play an important role

in sustaining these networks, as many of the most influential researchers are affiliated with graduate programs that encourage publication and academic cooperation.

The lack of a more decentralized collaboration structure may pose a challenge for the expansion of the subfield of the Teaching of Sociology, as the inclusion of new researchers in the network seems to depend on prior connections with already established agents (Bodart, 2024c). Furthermore, this study suggests that the reproduction of these co-authorship networks is directly related to the symbolic struggle for academic recognition and the need to accumulate scientific capital, making participation in these spaces a strategic factor for researchers' legitimation in the area.

Although the consolidation of these networks has progressed in recent years, there are still challenges related to a more equitable distribution of collaboration opportunities and to the strengthening of the subfield's autonomy within the broader academic field of the Social Sciences (Bodart, 2024c).

Based on the data collected so far on the Field of the Teaching of Sociology and the research subfield of the Teaching of Sociology, we can infer that these are social spheres in the process of consolidation, in which a restricted group of researchers is being consecrated. However, there appears to be permeability for the entry of new agents and the acquisition of legitimacy. Although these spaces (field and subfield) are not completely closed, specific rules and mechanisms are already in place that make it difficult to convert capital accumulated in other fields, as well as to introduce habitus and norms from external spheres.

Conclusion

The Field of Sociology Teaching in Brazil - and its research subfield - has been undergoing a continuous process of institutionalization and consolidation, especially over the past two decades. The inclusion of Sociology as a mandatory subject in high school, established in 2008, has boosted not only teacher training and the development of teaching materials, but also the emergence of an academic space dedicated to research on the teaching of the discipline. This subfield is characterized

by disputes over the legitimation of the knowledge produced, articulations between academic and school-based agents, and political tensions related to Sociology's presence in the school curriculum.

Recent research has shown significant growth in scientific production about the Teaching of Sociology in Brazil, as evidenced by the increase in articles, specialized journals, academic events, and research groups registered in the Directory of CNPq research groups. The presence of academic journals dedicated to the subject strengthens the dissemination of this knowledge. Furthermore, academic events play a central role in fostering the academic community and building a scientific identity for the subfield.

However, despite the progress made, structural challenges persist that hinder the full consolidation of the subfield. The uneven distribution of research groups across the national territory, with a concentration in the South and Southeast regions, reflects historical disparities in Brazilian academia. In addition, the analysis of scientific production reveals a strong concentration of authorship, with a small number of researchers dominating article publication and the organization of thematic dossiers. The limited international presence of research on the Teaching of Sociology also emerges as an obstacle, restricting opportunities for academic exchange and recognition of this subfield on the global stage.

Another important aspect concerns the participation of women in scientific production on the Teaching of Sociology. Although they represent the majority of authors, women researchers still face institutional barriers in reaching positions of higher academic prestige, highlighting the need for policies that promote greater gender equity within the scientific field. Moreover, the structure of co-authorship networks shows a pattern of unequal collaboration, in which some researchers play a central role in shaping debates, while others remain on the margins of the main production networks.

This study reinforces the importance of continuing efforts to strengthen the Teaching of Sociology as a field of scientific knowledge and pedagogical practice.

Despite recent achievements, the discipline still faces challenges regarding its permanence in the curriculum, teacher training, and the recognition of academic research on the topic. The consolidation of the subfield will depend on the expansion of institutional spaces, the diversification of the agents involved, and the strengthening of ties between academia and basic education.

We draw attention to the need for further investigations. Comparative studies with other international contexts and with other fields and subfields of teaching in other areas of knowledge (especially Philosophy, which shares similar characteristics due to its recent inclusion in Brazilian basic education) may increase the visibility of research on the Teaching of Sociology in Brazil and foster academic collaborations. Furthermore, analyzing the factors that limit the presence of research groups outside major urban centers may help promote strategies to reduce such disparities. Lastly, studies that do not treat teachers and students in basic education merely as objects of analysis but include them as co-authors can help strengthen the connection between the research subfield and the realities of basic education.

We must increasingly recognize and strengthen the interconnection of the research subfield of Sociology Teaching and the broader Field of Sociology Teaching, moving forward in the direction proposed by Pereira (2022): reinforcing the articulation between schools and academia, and promoting the consolidation of a shared space with unique characteristics - capable of integrating scientific production and pedagogical practice.

References

- Antunes, K. C. V., Garcia, E. A. S., & Alves, A. F. A. (2018). O ensino de Sociologia retratado nas teses e dissertações entre 1996 e 2015: Um estado da arte. *CSONline*, 28.
- Azevedo, G. C. de. (2014). *Sociologia no ensino médio: Uma trajetória político-institucional (1982-2008)* [Dissertação de mestrado, Universidade Federal Fluminense].
- Bazzo, V., & Scheibe, L. (2019). De volta para o futuro... Retrocessos na atual política de formação docente. *Revista Retratos da Escola*, 13(27), 669–684.
- Bodart, C. N. (2024a). A (des)concentração da produtividade de papers científicos sobre o Ensino de Sociologia no Brasil. *Simbiótica*, 11, 11–34.

- Bodart, C. N. (2024b). As mulheres e o subcampo de pesquisa do Ensino de Sociologia. *Tensões Mundiais*, 20(44).
- Bodart, C. N. (2024c). Redes de colaboração autoral no Ensino de Sociologia: Identificando microrredes e agentes sociais. *Pro-Posições*, 35, e2024c1104BR.
- Bodart, C., & Cigales, M. P. (2017). Ensino de Sociologia no Brasil (1993-2015): Um estado da arte na pós-graduação. *Revista de Ciências Sociais (UFC)*, 48, 256–281.
- Bodart, C. N., & Feijo, F. (2020). As Ciências Sociais no currículo do ensino médio brasileiro. *Revista Espaço do Currículo*, 13, 219–234.
- Bodart, C. N., Santos, F. C. M. dos, & Nascimento, V. M. da S. (2024). O Ensino de Sociologia no Diretório de Grupos de Pesquisa do CNPq (2023). *Tensões Mundiais*, 20(44).
- Bourdieu, P. (2017). *Homo academicus* (2ª ed.). Editora UFSC.
- Bourdieu, P. (2021). *Sociologia geral. Vol. 2: Habitus e campo. Curso no Collège de France (1982-1983)*. Vozes.
- Brunetta, A. A., Bodart, C. N., & Cigales, M. P. (Orgs.). (2020). *Dicionário do ensino de Sociologia*. Editora Café com Sociologia.
- Handfas, A. (2013). O estado da arte do ensino de Sociologia na educação básica: Um levantamento preliminar da produção acadêmica. *Revista Inter-legere*, 13.
- Mocelin, D. G. (2020). O ensino de Sociologia e seu campo. In A. A. Brunetta, C. N. Bodart, & M. P. Cigales (Orgs.), *Dicionário do ensino de Sociologia* (pp. 57–62). Editora Café com Sociologia.
- Oliveira, A. (2023). *O campo do ensino de Sociologia no Brasil: Gênese, agentes e disputas*. Editora Café com Sociologia.
- Oliveira, A., & Cigales, M. (2019). O ensino de Sociologia no Brasil: Um balanço dos avanços galgados entre 2008 e 2017. *Revista Temas em Educação*, 28(2), 42–58.
- Pereira, T. I. (2017). Sociologia escolar e associações científicas: A AB ECS como estratégia de luta. *Revista Eletrônica Interações Sociais*, 1(2), 18–29.
- Pereira, L. H. (2020). O ensino de Sociologia e os observatórios de ensino. In A. A. Brunetta, C. N. Bodart, & M. P. Cigales (Orgs.), *Dicionário do ensino de Sociologia* (pp. 201–205). Editora Café com Sociologia.
- Pereira, T. I. (2022). A centralidade do campo do ensino de Ciências Sociais/Sociologia brasileiro: Notas para um debate crítico. *Cadernos da Associação Brasileira do Ensino de Ciências Sociais (Cabecs)*, 6(2), 155–175.
- Schnekenberg, G. F. (2020). Dicionário do ensino de Sociologia: Retrato de uma área entre a escola e a universidade. *Revista Perspectiva Sociológica*, 26, 154–158.